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D5.10 Virtualized Policy Management V1

(Version 1.0, 08/02/2023)

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Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BDV	Big Data Value
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CRISP-DM	Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DB	DataBase
DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HPC	Cloud and High Performance Computing
IaaS	Infrastructure-as-a-Service
IdP	Identity Provider
IM	Instant Messaging
KDD	Knowledge Discovery in Databases
ML	Machine Learning
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
NER	Named-Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OIDC	OpenID Connect
PaaS	Platform-as-a-Service

PKCE	Proof Key for Code Exchange
RA	Reference Architecture
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
SSH	Secure Shell Protocol
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
VM	Virtual Machine
VO	Virtual Organisation
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package
XAI	eXplainable AI
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Executive summary

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies.

AI4PublicPolicy will provide public authorities, public administrators and other policy making stakeholders with a complete environment for AI-based policy making. Policy makers will be able to design, develop, deploy, validate and fine-tune data-driven, evidence-based policies from a single-entry point.

The AI4PublicPolicy Policy Making Process leverages on the CRISP-DM methodology to address the following objectives:

- Provide a data-driven, AI-based and evidence-based approach
- Promote and facilitate the collaboration between Policy Makers and AI Experts
- Involve citizens and other stakeholders in the Policy evaluation and optimization
- Boost the acceptance of the policies presenting and explaining the Policy development outcomes
- Reuse and share the Policy development models and Datasets across different domains and countries

AI4PublicPolicy will result in an online platform VPME which will be the main interface and host all the projects modules.

The components of VPME's first version architecture are divided into three main subsystems or pillars:

- Reusable and Interoperable Dataset
 - Dataset & Policy Management
 - Cross Country Interoperability
 - Datasets Catalogue
- Policy Extraction and Evaluation
 - Text and Sentiment Analysis
 - Policy Extraction
 - Policy Evaluation and Optimization

The AI4PublicPolicy platform is built on top of the multi-layered EOSC Compute Platform and the first version of the VPME implements the AI-based Policy Making process main high level scenarios described in D2.7 "Conceptual model and reference architecture V2" ^[1].

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens' participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realisation of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organisation transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project's AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project's developments. AI4PublicPolicy's business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercialising the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project's platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of Work Package 5

Work Package 5 (WP5) is the main integration point for all the components built in the tasks WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6. The key goal of this WP is to deliver the core outcome of the project which will also provide the policy makers with a single point of access to the resources.

The main objectives of WP5 are to:

- Analyse various datasets to obtain actionable insights through AI tools that range from sentiment analysis and text.
- Include citizens in the loop of policies implementation through a citizen-centric approach to obtain feedback and continuously evaluate and optimise the policies.
- Deliver the policy management environment (VPME) for creating, customising, linking / comparing, simulating, evaluating and optimising policies.
- Provide the required computing and data resources for performing the aforementioned AI analytics by dynamically allocating the required cloud resources.

1.3 Relation to other WPs and tasks

This deliverable presents the first version of the EOSC-based Virtualized Policy Management Environment which is the main interface point of the AI4PublicPolicy platform. The VPME once completed aims to provide a complete policy management framework over an existing open analytics environment that will: (i) enable creation, utilisation and adaptation of policies models (from WP3), (ii) incorporate APIs to trigger the execution of the AI models and techniques (T5.1/T5.2), including support from AutoML approaches (T4.5), (iii) enable the invocation and exploitation of the explainability AI mechanisms outcomes (T4.1 and T4.2), (iv) provide interfaces to the security technologies (T4.3 and T4.4), (v) facilitate the interplay with citizens and businesses through the techniques developed in T5.3, and (vii) integrate a visualisation environment to facilitate information provisioning for different datasets and analytics outcomes in an adaptive and dynamic way towards the policy makers and the public administrators. This task will run until the end of the project, to fine-tune the VPME based on feedback from the pilot operations in WP6.

1.4 Purpose and scope of the document

This deliverable addresses the first implementation of the Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME). The main user experience as also the registration and login and the main functionalities are described and demonstrated. Further on the document also presents the components integration and deployment.

1.5 Structure of the document

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

- The **first chapter** of the document presents an introduction to the project and the document.
- The **second chapter** of the document presents the main user experience (UX/UI).
- The **third chapter** of the document presents the registration and login process.
- The **fourth chapter** of the document presents the VPME functionalities
- The **fifth chapter** of the document presents the components integration.

- The **sixth chapter** of the document presents the components deployment.
- The **seventh chapter** of the document presents the conclusions and future works.

2 Main User Experience (UX/UI)

The front-end design of AI4PublicPolicy VPME is based on the principles of **intuitiveness** and **ease of navigation** for all users. Hence, the VPME interfaces are set up following a common graphical environment which draws from the project's visual identity and colour patterns as these have been introduced in *D8.1 - Initial Publication Package* and *D8.2 - Dissemination, Communication and Collaboration Plan and Activities V1^[1]*. The uniformed look and feel of VPME interfaces showcases the platforms readiness and continuity covering both hedonic qualities such as the layout properties and novelties of the interfaces, and -subsequently- ergonomic qualities like comprehensiveness, responsiveness and clarity of process flow.

Figure 2. Project logo

- **blue:** #2682C4
- **green:** #9AC742
- **dark-blue:** #1E4384
- **orange:** #E87F4C

Figure 3. Project colour patterns

ViLabs has provided technical partners with CSS and HTML documentation as well as a set of interactive mockups of the platform, in order to facilitate the delivery of VPME components in accordance with the above-mentioned properties. The interactive mockups include a login interface, a landing homepage and an example of component sub-page, all accompanied by the necessary CSS and HTML files, to be utilised as templates by the development leading partners.

First the login interface introduces the user to the AI4PublicPolicy VPME presenting a short catch-phrase and explaining the access process in four brief and concise steps which summarise the registration process (see Chapter 3).

Figure 4. AI4PublicPolicy VPME Login in/Sign up interface

Upon the successful log in/sign in, the VPME user is redirected to the platform’s homepage where access to the main components is available.

Figure 5. AI4PublicPolicy VPME Homepage

The VPME user may select to work on the Datasets components where he/she is presented with the available datasets of the different project pilots (in accordance with his/her selection during the registration process detailed in Chapter 3). The component interface provides the user the component-specific functionalities which are featured, based on the project colour patterns thus enabling an easy-to-grasp usage.

Figure 6. AI4PublicPolicy VPME Datasets component interface

3 Registration and Login

Registration and login to the VPME application has been developed in such a way so as to combine, in the best way possible, the project’s partners technological offerings along with the custom made solutions developed in the project and at the same time to have the least effort from the user’s side in his attempt to register to the platform. Thus, the registration to the EGI Check-In allows the user to be recognised on the VPME with the correct permissions. EGI Check-in is a proxy service that operates as a central hub to connect federated Identity Providers (IdPs) with EGI service providers. Check-in allows users to select their preferred IdP so that they can access and use EGI services in a uniform and easy way and in particular it is used by the VPME to verify the identity and level of access. The registration to Check-In requires, as a first step, the use of an existing account in one of the recognized IdP (e.g., public institutions accounts, universities and social media accounts and mail providers) which can be found in the figure below.

Figure 7. AI4PublicPolicy EGI Check-In page

Though many IdPs can be used, the easier, simplest and most common way is login through a Gmail account which most of the users possess. The steps to access the VPME application through an individual Gmail account are simple and are shown below. Firstly, the user has to reach the VPME’s Sign up/Log in page.

Figure 8. AI4PublicPolicy VPME Homepage

By clicking the Sign up/Log in button, the user is redirected to the EGI's check in page where can be chosen the "LOG IN WITH GOOGLE" option as indicated in the photo below.

Figure 9. AI4PublicPolicy EGI Google Check-In

By pressing the Login button, the user is prompted to the SIGN UP of EGI. By pressing "SIGNUP" button we are directed to Google's page in order to provide our credentials (i.e., only in case we are not logged in the browser used) as seen in the photos presented.

Figure 10. AI4PublicPolicy EGI Sign-Up

Figure 11. AI4PublicPolicy Google Account

After providing the Gmail account credentials, the user is asked to review and agree with EGI’s “Acceptable Use Policy” and to submit the form pre-filled with his/her personal details and to grant access to the VPME service as shown in the figure below.

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Figure 12. AI4PublicPolicy Signing to EGI

The screenshot shows the EGI User Community registration form. At the top, there is the EGI logo and the text "EGI User Community". The form fields are as follows:

- EGI ID:** A text field containing a long alphanumeric string: "user/6:79d74dbcbda8d09c09ad7671a2b6b-43c194216879421511a6ff6c35a23345@egi.eu".
- Name* (your full name):** A text field containing "Dimitris*" and "Baines".
- First name*:** A text field containing "Dimitris".
- Last name*:** A text field containing "Baines".
- Email (your current email address):** A text field containing "dbainesworktest@gmail.com".
- Affiliation:** A dropdown menu with "Faculty" selected.
- Organisation:** A text field containing "Organisation*".
- Agree to Acceptable Use Policy and Conditions of Use (AUP):** A section with the text "You must review and agree to the following AUP before continuing." Below this, there is a link "EGI Check-in Acceptable Use Policy" and a row of radio buttons: "Review Acceptable Use Policy" (selected) and "Agree".
- Footer:** A note stating "After you click Submit, we may send you an email and you simply click on a link to confirm your email address." Below this is a "SUBMIT" button and a note "*denotes required field".

At the bottom, there are logos for GRNET and the European Union, along with "Terms" and "Privacy" links. A copyright notice at the very bottom reads: "Copyright ©2016-2023 | Check-in is an EGI service provided by GRNET, receiving funding from the EGI Foundation (EGI.eu) and the EGI-ACE project (Horizon 2020) under Grant number 101017567 | Powered by RCI4M".

Figure 13. AI4PublicPolicy EGI form

Figure 14. AI4PublicPolicy Signing to EGI

Figure 15. AI4PublicPolicy Grant access to VPME

After this simple registration to the platform, the user is redirected automatically to the application. However, before entering the platforms main page and accessing its modules, the user has to register to the organisation to which he/she belongs or has interest to. The process is fairly simple, the user has to choose the membership which is the organisation of the project (AI4PublicPolicy), then the sub-groups in the “VO Group” field, which corresponds to the five project’s pilots (Athens, Burgas, Genoa, Lisbon and Nicosia) and finally the role the user wants to have within the system (Policy Maker or AI Expert). After having completed the form it is only needed to check the “Agree” check-box and submit the form as shown in the figures.

Figure 16. AI4PublicPolicy Join VO Group

Figure 17. AI4PublicPolicy Join VO - Select role

Figure 18. AI4PublicPolicy Join VO - Submit form

Figure 19. AI4PublicPolicy Join VO - Success message

After having successfully completed all the steps described, the user receives a “Successful Group & VO Registration” and is granted access to VPME’s application main module page as shown in the figure below. Now that the user is officially registered to the platform each time needs to Login to the platform, it is only required to choose the Gmail account choice in the EGI’s page that will be redirected and just to Login to his Gmail account. After this he will be immediately prompted to the VO page but the page will inform him that he is already registered to a virtual organisation (VO) and by pressing the “Ok” button he will be redirected to VPME’s main page.

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Figure 20. AI4PublicPolicy LogIn - Redirect to homepage

Figure 21. AI4PublicPolicy LogIn - Homepage

Although the registration with the Google account is the easiest and recommended way to SignUP and LogIn to the platform, if the user does not want to use it, EGI offers the option to obtain a Single Sign On (SSO) account that can be created by following the link on the bottom of the Check-In login page "Can't find your identity provider?". Clicking the link shows the following screen that explains the available options:

Figure 22. AI4PublicPolicy EGI SSO account

The first link allows the creation of an EGI SSO that will be linked to the email provided:

Figure 23. AI4PublicPolicy EGI SSO - Mail submission

After providing an email address a link, valid for 24 hours will be sent to the user. Following the link, the page shown in the following screenshot will be presented. This will allow the user to complete the registration to the EGI SSO

EGI registration

Your email address depaht23@getcae.com was successfully validated.
 You can create an account in the EGI Single Sign On domain here. The account is used for all EGI services.

You can use any UNICOD characters in the name.

user name

password

password (again)

full name

full name in English

surname in English

given name in English

organisation

job role

gender

work postal address

newsletter I would like to receive EGI's newsletter
By creating this account you are considered to be an interested recipient of our newsletter. Newsletter is the given email address.

Figure 24. AI4PublicPolicy EGI SSO - Filling Form

The EGI SSO account can be then accessed, modified or deleted at the following URL: <https://sso-admin.egi.eu/admin/user>.

At this point, with the newly created EGI SSO account the user is able to access the VPME's main page and proceed to Login into the platform by choosing the EGI SSO option on EGI's list of choices instead of Google identity provider. After this all the remaining steps needed are the same as described before.

AI4PublicPolicy VPME

An open Virtualized Policy Management Environment for **automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management** based on unique AI technologies

Get access in only 4 steps

- 1 Sign up/Log in using an Identity Provider
- 2 Signup to the EGI Community
- 3 Join a Virtual Organization
- 4 Receive authorized access to the AI4PublicPolicy VPME!

Figure 25. AI4PublicPolicy EGI SSO account Login

Figure 26. AI4PublicPolicy EGI SSO account

3.1 VPME Service Provider configuration

To implement the processes described in the previous sections, AI4PublicPolicy VPME has been added as a service provider in the EGI Federation registry and configured to manage an OpenID Connect authentication flow ^[2] with EGI Check-in.

The screenshot displays the EGI Federation Registry interface. At the top center is the EGI logo and the text "EGI Federation Registry". Below this is a breadcrumb trail: "Home / Manage Services / View Service". A blue notification bar states "Service was registered at: 2023/01/06 03:07:19". On the left, a navigation menu is organized into three sections: MAIN (Manage Services), PERSONAL (Invitations, User Information), and FEDERATION (All Services). The main content area has two tabs: "General" (selected) and "Protocol Specific". Under the "General" tab, the following fields are visible: "Service name" (AI4PublicPolicy VPME), "Integration Environment" (Development), "Logo" (https://ai4publicpolicy.eu/pbl-uploads/2021/03/AI4PublicPolicy_Logo_01.png), "Service Website URL" (https://ai4publicpolicy.eu/the-vpme-2/), and "Description" (Virtualized Policy Management Environment for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The platform provides fully-fledged policy).

Figure 27. VPME Service Provider - General Information

The OIDC configuration specifies the valid redirect URIs for login and logout, the scopes allowed, the grant types, the tokens timeout and implements an OAUTH2 authentication code flow with PKCE enabled [3].

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General
Protocol Specific

Select Protocol * OIDC Service

Client ID vmpe_ai4pp
Unique identifier. If you leave this blank it will be automatically generated.

Application Type * Web Native
Kind of the application. Web Clients MUST only register URLs using the https scheme as redirect_uris; they MAY use the http scheme when using localhost as the hostname. Native Clients MUST only register redirect_uris using custom URI schemes or URLs using the http scheme with localhost as the hostname.

Redirect URI(s) *
https://vpme.ai4publicpolicy.eu/*
https://*.ai4publicpolicy.eu/*
URLs that the client can be redirected to. Different URI validation rules apply depending on the application type.

Post Logout Redirect URI(s)
https://vpme.ai4publicpolicy.eu/*
URLs to request that the End-User's browser be redirected after a logout has been performed using the post_logout_redirect_uri parameter.

Scope *

openid	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
voperson_id	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
email	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
profile	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
offline_access	<input type="checkbox"/>
eduperson_entitlement	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
eduperson_scoped_affiliation	<input type="checkbox"/>
eduperson_unique_id	<input type="checkbox"/>
aarc	<input type="checkbox"/>
orcid	<input type="checkbox"/>

OAuth scopes this client is allowed to request. See [here](#) for more information.

Grant Types * authorization code
 client credentials
 token-exchange
 device code
 implicit (deprecated)

Token Endpoint Authorization Method * Client Secret over HTTP Basic
 Client Secret over HTTP POST
 Client Secret via symmetrically-signed JWT assertion
 Asymmetrically-signed JWT assertion
 No authentication

Introspection Allow calls to the Introspection Endpoint?
Access to the Token Introspection endpoint is restricted to confidential clients.

Refresh Tokens Refresh tokens are issued for this client
This will add the offline_access scope to the client's scopes.

Device Code Device code is issued for this client
This will add the device grant type to your grant types.

Proof Key for Code Exchange (PKCE) Code Challenge Method * SHA-256 hash algorithm (recommended)
▲ Enabling PKCE is highly recommended to avoid code injection and code replay attacks. If enabled, you need to make sure that your client uses PKCE to prevent errors

Access Token Timeout * 3600 seconds
Enter this time in seconds, minutes, or hours (Max value is 1000000 seconds (11.5 days)).

ID Token Timeout * 600 seconds
Enter this time in seconds, minutes, or hours (Max value is 86400 seconds (1 day)).

Figure 28. VPME Service Provider - Protocol Information

The VPME Service Provider configuration has been setup in the development (DEV) environment first and then cloned to the Demo environment after having successfully tested the flow.

The screenshot shows the EGI Federation Registry interface. At the top, the EGI logo and 'EGI Federation Registry' title are visible. Below the title is a navigation bar with 'Home / Manage Services'. A sidebar on the left contains navigation links for 'MAIN' (Manage Services), 'PERSONAL' (Invitations, User Information), and 'FEDERATION' (All Services). The main content area has a 'Manage Services' header with 'Refresh', '+ New Service', 'Show Filters', and a search box. Below this, there are two service cards for 'AI4PublicPolicy VPME'. The first card is labeled 'Dev' and 'Deployed', and the second is labeled 'Demo' and 'Deployed'. Both cards provide a detailed description of the platform and include 'View' and 'Reconfigure' buttons.

Figure 29. VPME Service Provider environments

4 VPME Functionalities

4.1 Datasets and Policy Management

The dataset and policy management component provides an application to define and collect datasets from different sources and to define policies. This component is developed under Task T3.1 “Data Management and API for Data Collection” and described in more detail in deliverables D3.1 “Data Management and APIs for Data Collection v1” and D3.2 “Data Management and APIs for Data Collection v2” [1]. The dataset and policy management component is a central component in the AI4PublicPolicy platform. Datasets provided by different stakeholders are stored in EGI DataHub and shared with others in case these datasets are public. Datasets are used by the different AI models that implement a policy. Policies are defined and stored in a database. Both datasets and policies can be accessed by other components of the AI4PublicPolicy platform through their respective REST APIs. In addition, a web interface has been developed. This interface allows non-technical users to define dataset schemas and policies, add datasets and visualise the policies and datasets available on the platform. The web interface is embedded within the VPME.

Dataset Definition and Management

The Datasets tab within the web interface allows the user to visualise all datasets defined within the AI4PublicPolicy platform, define a new dataset schema and upload a dataset (Figure 29).

Figure 30. Dataset definition and management menu

The dataset definition interface presented in Figure 31, allows users of the VPME to define a new dataset schema by filling in a form with the structure of the dataset. As first step, the user selects from the dropdown menu the area to which the dataset will be associated (energy, water infrastructure management, optimization of city resources, urban mobility). After this, the user has to write the name of the dataset schema, the description, the owner, the language and specify the dataset type from the available ones (csv, json, excel, image). If an image is selected, its format (jpg, png, ...) must also be indicated otherwise, the user has to define the fields of the dataset.

Figure 31. Dataset schema definition web interface

Once a dataset is defined, it is possible to upload dataset files both from an endpoint and from EGI DataHub. Figure 32 shows the web interface that allows the user to add new dataset files with a particular dataset schema. If the user decides to upload a dataset file from an endpoint, he/she has to fill in a form for selecting the area, the dataset and specifying the endpoint where the dataset is available from. In this second case, the dataset is automatically downloaded and stored in the EGI DataHub platform. On the other hand, if the user decides to upload the dataset to the EGI DataHub platform, clicking on the “EGI DataHub” button of the web interface opens the EGI DataHub interface in another tab of the web browser.

Figure 32. Dataset uploading web interface

The web interface allows the user to inspect all defined datasets and the files stored in each dataset. Figure 33 shows the web interface where all available areas are depicted. Selecting one of the areas, for instance “Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance”, the available datasets are shown, such as “Logger Laka” and “Scenario 0”.

Selecting the “Scenario 0” dataset, the list of available dataset files is presented. In this case only one dataset file is uploaded in the EGI DataHub, “Scenario0_tag_AllTapsClosed.csv”. The web interface also allows the download of a dataset file by clicking on the “Download” button.

Figure 33. Dataset management web interface

Policy definition and management

Figure 34 shows the web interface used for the definition of policies. To do so, the user selects the area and fills in the form indicating the name of the policy, the owner, a description and the purpose of the policy. It also allows associating datasets to policies. These datasets have to be previously defined through the dataset definition web interface or through a call to the REST API. Finally, the user indicates the policy KPIs and presses the submit button to create the new policy.

Navbar Home Policy Datasets AI Model Search Search

Policy Definition

Register a new policy

Area
-- Select an area --

Policy Name Owner

Policy description

Objective

Policy Datasets Add Dataset
SELECT THE DATASETS TO BE USED IN THIS POLICY

Dataset
Select from available datasets X
Indicate the dataset to be used in the policy from the available ones. This field can be empty and be filed latter.

Policy KPIs definition Add KPI
DEFINE THE KEY INDICATORS TO ESTIMATE FOR THIS POLICY

KPI #1

Submit

Figure 34. Policy definition web interface

Figure 35 shows the web interface implemented to allow changes to an existing policy. The form that appears is similar to the one used for the definition. However, in this case, the user only selects the area and the policy. All fields are then filled in with the current values, which can be modified and saved.

Navbar Home Policy Datasets AI Model Search Search

AI4PublicPolicy

Policy Update

Update a policy

Area
-- Select an area --

Policy Select the policy Owner

Policy description

Objective

Policy Datasets DATASETS USED IN THE POLICY Add Dataset

Policy KPIs definition KPIS OF THE POLICY Add KPI

Submit

Figure 35. Policy update web interface

Figure 36 shows the list of available policies. Selecting the area of interest, the different policies appear. In this case in the "Energy Management" area there is one policy: "PV systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon". The associated information is also shown.

Figure 36. Policy management web interface

4.2 Cross Country Interoperability & Policy Sharing

The cross-country interoperability and policy sharing component translates policies and dataset definitions from one language to another. This facilitates the reuse of different policies and datasets in different countries with different languages. This component has been developed under Task T3.3 *Cross Country Policy Interoperability and Sharing*. This component currently uses Google Cloud Translation library for the translation. Once a translation is made, it is stored internally to avoid delays and reduce the costs.

Figure 37 shows the available policies presented in section 2.1.1 with the translation functionality integrated. When the user accesses the policies web interface, the policies defined are shown. In this case, there are two policies defined for the “Management and Optimization of City Resources” area: *Optimised parking space allocation* and *Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes*. Both policies were defined in English as can be seen in the drop-down menu of each policy description.

Home Policy Datasets XAI Search Search

AI4PublicPolicy VPME

Policies

Areas

- Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility
- Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
- Citizens and Business Services Optimisation
- Management and Optimisation of City Resources
- Energy Management

POLICIES

Policies in: english

Optimized parking space allocation More Information Translate into english Delete

Identify on-street parking areas with high/low parking requests, so parking spaces between residents and guests can be allocated more efficiently to enable optimal use of space and high revenues for the City.

Datasets: Wallet transactions, Parking transactions, Incident management reports act, Incident management reports

Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes More Information Translate into english Delete

Predict maintenance incidents in the next months to plan material purchases and plan seasonal personnel.

Datasets: Wallet transactions, Parking transactions, Incident management reports act, Incident management reports

Figure 37. Policies defined in English for the “Management and Optimisation of City Resources” Area

A dropdown menu allows the user to list all policies available for a particular area and language. As presented in Figure 38, the policies for the *Management and Optimization of City Resources* area in Spanish are listed. In this case, only the *Optimised parking space allocation* policy is available in Spanish.

Policies

Areas

The 'Areas' section displays five policy areas, each with an icon and a title. The 'Management and Optimisation of City Resources' area is highlighted with a purple border. The areas are:

- Holistic and Accessible Urban Mobility (Megaphone icon)
- Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance (Water drop icon)
- Citizens and Business Services Optimisation (Bar chart icon)
- Management and Optimisation of City Resources (City buildings icon)
- Energy Management (Hands holding a lightning bolt icon)

POLICIES

Policies in: spanish ▾

Optimized parking space allocation [More Information](#) Translate to spanish ▾ [Delete](#)

Identificar áreas de estacionamiento en la calle con solicitudes de estacionamiento altas/bajas, para que los espacios de estacionamiento entre residentes e invitados se puedan asignar de manera más eficiente para permitir un uso óptimo del espacio y altos ingresos para la ciudad.

Datasets:

Figure 38. Policies in Spanish for the “Management and Optimisation of City Resources” Area

The drop-down menu of each policy description allows users to translate a policy into another language. Internally, if the policy is not already translated, it is processed with the Google Cloud Translation API, stored into a database and shown to the user. Otherwise, the translation step is omitted and the policy in the requested language is obtained from the internal database. Figure 39 shows the translation of the *Optimised parking space allocation* into Greek.

Policies

Areas

Holistic and Accessible Urban Mobility

Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance

Citizens and Business Services Optimisation

Management and Optimisation of City Resources

Energy Management

POLICIES

Policies in: english ▼

Optimized parking space allocation
[More Information](#)
Translate to greek ▼
Delete

Προσδιορίστε περιοχές στάθμευσης στο δρόμο με υψηλά/χαμηλά αιτήματα στάθμευσης, έτσι ώστε οι θέσεις στάθμευσης μεταξύ των κατοίκων και των επισκεπτών να μπορούν να κατανεμηθούν πιο αποτελεσματικά για τη βέλτιστη χρήση του χώρου και τα υψηλά έσοδα για την πόλη.

Datasets:

Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes
[More Information](#)
Translate to english ▼
Delete

Predict maintenance incidents in the next months to plan material purchases and plan seasonal personnel.

Datasets:

Figure 39. Policy translation into Greek

Finally, when the user clicks on the “More Information” button, the objective and the KPIs are shown in the same language as the police is requested. Figure 40, shows the objective and KPIs for the *Optimised parking space allocation* policy in Greek.

Management and Optimisation of City Resources

Energy Management

POLICIES

Policies in: english ▾

Optimized parking space allocation [More Information](#) Translate to greek ▾ [Delete](#)

Προσδιορίστε περιοχές στάθμευσης στο δρόμο με υψηλά/χαμηλά αιτήματα στάθμευσης, έτσι ώστε οι θέσεις στάθμευσης μεταξύ των κατοίκων και των επισκεπτών να μπορούν να καταμερισθούν πιο αποτελεσματικά για τη βέλτιστη χρήση του χώρου και τα υψηλά έσοδα για την πόλη.

Datasets:

Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes [More Information](#) Translate to english ▾ [Delete](#)

Predict maintenance incidents in the next months to plan material purchases and plan seasonal personnel.

Datasets:

Optimized parking space allocation

Objective: Οι διαθέσιμες θέσεις στάθμευσης στην Αθήνα επισημαίνονται στο δρόμο και κατανέμονται μεταξύ κατοίκων της πόλης (απαιτείται ειδική άδεια) και επισκεπτών (πληρωμή μέσω εφαρμογής στάθμευσης). Ως εκ τούτου, με αυτήν την πολιτική ο Δήμος Αθηναίων θα ήθελε να διαθέσει πιο αποτελεσματικά τους διαθέσιμους χώρους μεταξύ κατοίκων και φιλοξενουμένων, ώστε να μην μένουν αχρησιμοποίητοι ή λείπουν χώροι κάθε εποχή.

Name	KPIs
Description	Description
Ποσοστό κάλυψης θέσεων στάθμευσης	
Έσοδα από θέσεις στάθμευσης επισκεπτών	
Ικανοποίηση πολιτών	

Figure 40. Policy details translation into Greek

4.3 Policy Extraction

The Policy Extraction Toolkit component enables the extraction of data-driven policies based on selected AI algorithms (including Machine Learning, Deep Learning and Reinforcement learning) to estimate and recommend the parameters of the policy models, based on the policy datasets.

A web interface for the policy extraction component consists of two main views:

- AI Expert view
- Policy Maker view

AI Expert view provides an interface to the AI expert which allows them to select a project, policy KPI and start working on the project:

Figure 41. Policies to extract - AI Expert view

If the AI project for selected policy KPI doesn't exist yet then it could be created by clicking "Create AI project".

Figure 42. AI project creation

Once the AI project is created the AI Expert can open it in the Open Analytical Environment (JupyterHub) clicking on "Manage AI project" and start to experiment with Jupyter notebooks to train and validate an AI Model.

Figure 43. Jupyter notebook development

Clicking on “View experiments” button the AI Expert could compare the experiment and optimize the model.

Figure 44. Experiments comparison

The policy maker view provides a policy maker ability to test and compare AI models for a selected project and policy KPI. In this view the policy maker first has to choose the project to be opened.

Figure 45. Policies to extract – Policy Maker view

Once the project is opened, the policy maker selects a policy KPI and an AI model to test.

D5.10 Virtualized Policy Management Environment V1

PV systems mapping for climate neutral Lisbon (US?)

To monitor the yearly achieved PV capacity based on the identification of existing systems locations and, when possible, further characterization.

Select Policy KPI

- % Predicted installed capacity versus actual installed capacity (K0)
- % Predicted installation area versus actual installation area (K1)
- % Predicted number of installations versus actual number of installations (K2)
- % Predicted number of panels versus actual number of panels (K3)
- % Predicted location of building installations versus actual building location of installations (K4)

Select AI Model

- AI Model test (K2)

Test AI Model

Tested AI Models

- AI Model test (K2)

Select AI Model **Compare AI Models** **Delete**

Figure 46. AI Models test

After testing all the available AI Models the Policy Maker can compare their performance metrics clicking on “Compare AI Models”, evaluate the model results saved as artifacts and then select the best model for the KPI.

mlflow 2.1.1 Experiments Models

Lisbon Pilot

Track machine learning training runs in experiments. Learn more

Experiment ID: 0 Artifact Location: mlflow-artifacts/0

Description Edit

metrics: mse < 1 and params:model = "tree"

Sort: Created Columns Refresh

Time created: All time State: Active Showing 4 matching runs

Run Name	Created	Duration	Source	Models
Lisbon (train)	9 days ago	38.4min	[p] lisbon2tr...	-
Lisbon (detect)	9 days ago	56.2s	[p] lisbon2tr...	YoloV5 mod.../1
overjoyed-smelt-885	9 days ago	30.9s	[p] lisbon2tr...	-
dapper-rook-63	12 days ago	8.6s	[p] spykernel...	-

Load more

Show more metrics and parameters (70)

Figure 47. AI Models comparison

Figure 48. AI Model results

4.4 Policy Evaluation

The Policy Evaluation toolkit enables the simulation and evaluation of the developed AI policies taking into account the human factor, in particular, we use different types of surveys which can be declined on different channels. The surveys provided can ideally be linked to action strategies that can be implemented at different stages of a machine learning pipeline. The web application is composed by two logical views:

- the Policy Maker view;
- the Stakeholder view;

The Policy Maker view is similar to an admin portal, where a list that includes all the policies in EXTRACTED state is shown. For each of these policies the Policy Maker can manage and create custom surveys using the survey generator available in the toolkit.

Figure 49. Surveys' list

Two types of surveys are managed:

- App surveys, that could be visualized and completed by the stakeholders using their specific view in the application

Policy: Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people

Create a new survey

Enter the basic information about your new survey

Add more items to the survey clicking on the plus button below

Survey items

☰	Question: Policy maker question	Objective: Question objective..	Type: comment
---	---------------------------------	---------------------------------	---------------

Survey preview

[Hide](#)

Policy maker question *

Figure 50. App Survey Creator tool

- Social surveys, that result in posts on specific social account (on Twitter or Mastodon)

Home Datasets Policies[Go Back](#)

Policy: Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people

Post a tweet on Twitter

Survey name*

Tweet text*

Select end date

[Publish on Twitter](#)

Fetch a tweet from Twitter

Use this tool to retrieve a question posted on twitter by id and create a survey.

Survey name*

Tweet ID*

Select end date

[Fetch tweet](#)

Figure 51. Twitter Survey Creator tool

When a survey is closed, the Policy Maker can see the aggregated results using the appropriate dashboard.

From the perspective of stakeholders, citizens can compile the available surveys according to their participation in policies, thus participating with their feedback in the policy co-creation process.

The screenshot shows the 'AI4PublicPolicy VPME' logo in the top left and a 'Go Back' button in the top right. Below the header, the text 'Compile the survey' is displayed. The main content area contains three sections: 'Comment A' with a text input field, 'Ranking' with three radio button options labeled 1, 2, and 3, and 'Question rating' with a 5-point scale from 'Not Satisfied' to 'Completely satisfied'.

Figure 52. Stakeholder survey page

5 Components Integration

In this first version of the VPME the different components are integrated as separate applications linked in the VPME welcome page, using the same IAM system (EGI Check-in) and the same VPME Service Provider.

The `access_token` received from the VPME after the user login process is shared among the different applications, implementing a SSO mechanism, and it is used as authorization token to call the components' API.

The components' API, in fact, have been secured and validate the access_token to authorize the calls from client applications. Moreover, they could use the access_token to retrieve user's information.

The Policy Extraction component calls the Policy Management API to retrieve the policies in DEFINED state and to update the status or to link the extracted AI models. Additionally, it calls Sentiment Analysis API to evaluate the sentiment from answers to open questions or social survey responses.

The Policy Evaluation component calls the Policy Management API to retrieve the policies in EXTRACTED state and to update the status.

The Policy Management component calls the Cross-county interoperability API to translate policy's data.

The Marketplace Catalogue component calls the Dataset Management API to save an imported dataset.

5.1 API

5.1.1 Dataset management

The definition of new dataset schemas, the collection of datasets and the list of available datasets are managed through the REST API. Figure 44 shows the Swagger interface of the aforementioned REST API. Each of the different methods are used internally by the web interface.

Figure 53. Dataset management Swagger REST API

5.1.2 Policy management

The definition of new policies and their management is done through a REST API that provides several methods as shown in Figure 46. This REST API can be used by other components of the AI4PublicPolicy platform such as the Policy Extraction component.

policymanagement Show/Hide | List Operations | Expand Operations

DELETE	/policymanagement/policy/{policy_id}	Deletes the information stored about the requested policy
GET	/policymanagement/policy/{policy_id}	Returns the stored information about the requested policy
PUT	/policymanagement/policy/{policy_id}	Updates a specify policy
GET	/policymanagement/ai_models/{policy_id}	Returns the information of all the stored ai_models for a particular policy
DELETE	/policymanagement/ai_model/{ai_model_id}	Deletes the information stored about the requested ai_model
GET	/policymanagement/ai_model/{ai_model_id}	Returns the stored information about the requested ai_model
PUT	/policymanagement/ai_model/{ai_model_id}	Updates a specify ai_model
GET	/policymanagement/policies/{area}	Returns the stored information about the requested policy
GET	/policymanagement/policies	Returns the information of all the stored policies
POST	/policymanagement/ai_model	Adds a new ai_model
GET	/policymanagement/ai_models	Returns the information of all the stored ai_models
POST	/policymanagement/policy	Adds a new policy

[BASE URL: /ai4pp] UPGRADE {...}

Figure 54. Policy manager swagger REST API

5.1.3 Cross Country Interoperability & Policy Sharing

This component provides a REST API (Figure 47), that can be invoked by other components of the AI4PublicPolicy platform and is also used by the VPME.

Cross Country Interoperability 1.0.0 OAS3

/api/v3/openapi.json

This REST API

Some useful links:

- [Documentation](#)

Contact the developer

Apache 2.0

Servers: /api/v3

policy Policy translation operations

- GET /policy Return the policy information in the specified language
- PUT /policy Translate a policy from the original language to a particular one
- GET /policy/findByAreaAndLanguage Return all policies for a particular area and language

dataset Dataset translation operations

- PUT /dataset/file Translate a dataset file from the original language to a particular one
- PUT /dataset/schema Translate a dataset schema from the original language to a particular one

Figure 55. Cross Country Interoperability Swagger REST API

5.1.4 Policy extraction

The component provides a REST API for AI project creation, retrieving and running it.

The image shows a Swagger REST API interface for 'AI project'. It lists several endpoints with their respective HTTP methods and descriptions:

- POST** `/project` Create a new project
- GET** `/project/{projectId}` Get project by ID
- DELETE** `/project/{projectId}` Deletes a project
- GET** `/project/{user}/{kpi}/{policy}` Get project user, kpi and policy
- DELETE** `/project/{user}/{kpi}/{policy}` Deletes a project
- PUT** `/project/update` Update project
- GET** `/projects` Load policy project
- POST** `/project/run` Run the project

Figure 56. Policy Extraction Swagger REST API

5.1.5 Policy evaluation

The component provides a REST API for managing surveys and retrieving the results.

The image shows a Swagger REST API interface for 'Policy Evaluation API'. It includes a 'Servers' dropdown set to 'http://localhost:8000/'. The API is divided into two sections:

Surveys API for managing AI4PP surveys

- GET** `/surveys/policy/{policyId}` Get the Surveys of a Policy
- GET** `/surveys/{surveyId}` Get a survey by ID
- DELETE** `/surveys/{surveyId}` Delete a survey
- PUT** `/surveys/{surveyId}` Update a survey
- POST** `/surveys` Create a survey

Results API for managing AI4PP survey results

- POST** `/results` Post a survey result
- GET** `/results/{surveyId}` Get results list by survey id
- GET** `/results/{surveyId}/{policyId}/{period}` Get results list by survey id and policy id

Figure 57. Policy Evaluation Swagger REST API

5.1.6 Sentiment Analysis

For the sentiment analysis component, a REST API has been developed to provide the sentiment and emotion of the extracted text. The available API endpoints have been split by the type of source (comments or Twitter) and by task, which in this case is the sentiment and emotion classifications. This API has been integrated and used in the Policy Evaluation phase. Figure 49 shows the Swagger interface of the REST API.

Figure 58. Sentiment Analysis REST API

Comments analytics focuses on opinions posted by users about a particular entity. The available languages for both sentiment and emotion analysis are English (en), Greek (el), Italian (it), Portuguese(pt), and Bulgarian (bg). The available endpoints (Figure 23) and classes of each model can be found below:

Endpoint: `/sentiment/comments`

- Labels: positive, negative, neutral

Endpoint: `/emotion/comments`

- Labels: anger, disgust, joy, neutral, sadness, surprise

Text from tweets is usually noisy, so we are pre-processing and cleaning the input text to remove symbols such as (@, #, etc). Tweets are usually very different from other forms of comments or text on social media, because they are restricted to 280 characters and tend to be more opinionated than other forms. Supported languages are English(en), Greek (el), Italian (it), Portuguese(pt), Bulgarian (bg). The available endpoints and classes of each model can be found below:

Endpoint: `/sentiment/twitter`

- Labels: positive, negative, neutral

Endpoint: `/emotion/twitter`

- Labels: love, joy, sadness, surprise, anger, fear

5.2 Marketplace catalogue integration

The AI4PP Marketplace allows the usage of its data by external applications, the marketplace uses the authentication module to establish an authenticated connection with VPME allowing to insert new data including datasets on the VPME platform, the following image provides an overview on how different the platforms communicate with each other.

Figure 59. Integration overview

User interaction flow

The following flow illustrates how an user can select and add a dataset on the VPME through the integration with the AI4PP Marketplace.

Figure 60. Add dataset process flow

- **Authentication:** the user navigates to the AI4PP Marketplace through the VPME platform, in this process a User Access Token is provided to establish the authentication between both parties.
- **Listing and selecting the dataset:** the user is able to select a dataset from a list containing all the dataset.
- **Generate and customise the dataset:** the user will be able to customise the dataset, including the type of data that is measured, the period of time and the geographical location where the data was collected.
- **Store dataset:** after customising the dataset and the data be sent to the VPME platform, the dataset is then processed by the VPME processes and it will be available to be consulted by the platform users.

6 Components deployment

The current deployment of the VPME will be based on Kubernetes and it will use the same cluster used for the deployment of the EGI Notebooks dedicated to the AI4PublicPolicy project. Kubernetes has been chosen as it offers a way to deploy, scale and manage containerized applications. If additional resources are required, the Kubernetes cluster can be expanded and the additional resources used dynamically. The deployment of the VPME components is kept separated from the Notebooks one by using a different namespace and a dedicated user. This allows the AI4PublicPolicy to access the Kubernetes cluster nodes without the need to use a privileged user and access only the dedicated namespace. The namespaces provided by Kubernetes are a mechanism that allow the isolation of groups of resources that utilise the same Kubernetes cluster. The first namespace for the testing is currently configured and a new one for the production environment will be added. This will allow the testing of new versions of the VPME components before they are deployed to the production namespace.

To access the Kubernetes cluster, the public key of a restricted number of users has been added to the cluster machines on the authorised user list for the “ai4pp” user which will be used on the “ai4pp” namespace for the initial testing. To access this user the following command is used:

```
ssh -J ai4pp@193.225.251.116 ai4pp@192.168.0.77
```

The environment is currently ready and two examples of a test deployment for nginx and a corresponding ingress are provided. To deploy them the following commands have been used:

```
kubectl apply -f test-nginx.yaml -n ai4pp
kubectl apply -f ingress.yaml -n ai4pp
```

and the content of the respective files are shown in the following table:

Table 1. test-nginx.yaml

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: nginx-deployment
  labels:
    app: nginx
spec:
  replicas: 3
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: nginx
```

```
template:
  metadata:
    labels:
      app: nginx
  spec:
    containers:
      - name: nginx
        image: nginx:1.14.2
        ports:
          - containerPort: 80
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: my-nginx
  labels:
    app: nginx
spec:
  ports:
    - port: 80
      protocol: TCP
  selector:
    app: nginx
---
apiVersion: networking.k8s.io/v1
kind: Ingress
metadata:
  annotations:
    kubernetes.io/ingress.class: nginx
    # this is to avoid the 404 as the backend will get
    # as path /test/xxx, with this it becomes /xxx
    nginx.ingress.kubernetes.io/rewrite-target: /$2
  name: ingress-test
spec:
  rules:
```

```

- host: jupyterhub.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu
  http:
    paths:
      - pathType: Prefix
        path: "/test"
        backend:
          service:
            name: my-nginx
            port:
              number: 80

```

Following the above template, an MLflow¹ server has been deployed using the official MLflow Docker image. Table 2 shows the main differences with respect to the nginx deployment. Beside using a different container with its relative arguments, the ingress uses a different DNS hostname to avoid conflicts with the EGI Notebooks deployed on the same kubernetes cluster in a different namespace. The DNS hostname has been defined using the Dynamic DNS service² that allow users to register their chosen DNS hostnames in given domains and assign to public IPs of their servers both through a web user interface³ and HTTP API.

Table 2. mlflow.yaml

```

spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: mlflow
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: mlflow
    spec:
      containers:
        - image: ghcr.io/mlflow/mlflow
          imagePullPolicy: IfNotPresent
          name: mlflow

```

¹ <https://mlflow.org/>

² <https://docs.egi.eu/users/compute/cloud-compute/dynamic-dns/>

³ <https://nsupdate.fedcloud.eu/>

```
    command: ["mlflow"]
    args: ["server", "--host", "0.0.0.0", "--port", "8080"]
    ports:
      - containerPort: 8080
---
apiVersion: networking.k8s.io/v1
kind: Ingress
metadata:
  annotations:
    kubernetes.io/ingress.class: nginx
  name: ingress-mlflow
spec:
  rules:
  - host: mlflow.test.fedcloud.eu
    http:
      paths:
      - pathType: Prefix
        path: "/"
        backend:
          service:
            name: my-mlflow
            port:
              number: 8080
```

Figure 52 shows all the components described in Table 1 and 2. All the needed components can be deployed using a similar structure and, after the initial assessments and tests, the current Kubernetes cluster can be expanded as needed. The number of worker nodes can be increased to cope with increased resources requirements if needed and the number of namespaces can be as well increased for example by adding an additional namespace for the production environment that can be kept separated from the one used for the tests.

Figure 61. Kubernetes components deployment

7 Conclusions and Future Works

This deliverable illustrates the first version of the VPME that will be followed by two further versions that will be updating the current version and also include new features as they become gradually available.

The front-end design of the VPME is based on the principles of **intuitiveness** and **ease of navigation** for all users and utilises a common graphical environment which draws from the project's visual identity and colour patterns. Furthermore, the Signup and Login process is constructed by taking into account user's ease without disregarding security procedures and protocols.

In this first version of the deliverable, we present the Registration and Login Process as also the components that have been prepared and made available. These include: i) the Dataset and policy management component that provides an application to define and collect datasets from different sources and to define policies; ii) the cross-country interoperability component translates policies and dataset definitions from one language to another; iii) the Policy Extraction Toolkit component which enables the extraction of data-driven policies based on selected AI algorithms to estimate and recommend the parameters of the policy models, based on the policy datasets; and iv) the Policy Evaluation toolkit which enables the simulation and evaluation of the developed AI policies taking into account the human factor.

Following VPME's platform first version, ongoing refinements on already existing AI models will be applied as also new pilots use cases will be developed upon new data gathering. In addition, in the next versions of VPME an automated machine learning architecture will be applied in order to better orchestrate the development, supervision and comparison of the different AI models. This addition will make the platform able to better handle the amount of AI models built and will also permit the user to easily train, test and compare the different models he will build. Last but not least, the explainable AI model module under development will be refined which will aid users to better understand the predictions made by the models and to overall result in better policy decisions. VPME's first version aim was to create an easy to use and operate platform and to let the user use the basic operating modules from which valuable feedback will be gathered so as to refine and enhance the next versions.

VPME's second and third version will aim to apply the knowledge gained from the first version's feedback and by applying new operations and automations to result in a state-of-the-art AI driven policy making platform.

8 References

- [1] [AI4PublicPolicy deliverables](#)
- [2] https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-core-1_0.html
- [3] [Authorization Code Flow with Proof Key for Code Exchange \(PKCE\)](#)